

Ablaut Reduplicatives in English and Uzbek languages**Begimkulova Dilobar Baxtiyor qizi**Karshi State University (begimkulova9092@mail.ru)

Abstract: This article examines reduplication in the English and Uzbek languages as a phonological phenomenon. It also analyzes the phonological aspects, classification, and linguistic features of the formation of reduplicative units in a comparative manner.

Keywords: reduplication, ablaut reduplication, rhyming reduplication, replicatum, replican, shm-reduplication.

Аннотация: В данной статье редупликация в английском и узбекском языках изучается как фонологическое явление, а также сравнительно анализируются фонологические аспекты, классификация и лингвистические особенности образования редупликативных единиц.

Ключевые слова: Редупликация, аблаут-редупликация, рифмованная редупликация, репликатум, репликан, шм-редупликация.

Ablaut reduplicatives are formed by internal vowel change or apophony within a morpheme. According to M. Donka's research, written sources of the English language prior to the 15th century do not contain examples of ablaut reduplication. Today, however, the scholar notes that ablaut reduplicatives make up around 20-30% of all reduplicative examples, with 65% of them emerging in the 16th-17th centuries [5:139]. According to J.M. Dienhart's comparative studies, 73% of ablaut reduplicatives have developed over more than two centuries, and since the early 19th century, the productivity of this type of reduplication as a word-formation process has steadily declined [1:33].

In ablaut reduplicatives, the position of the replicatum or replican is not fixed. The lexical base may appear in the right half (e.g., *mingle-mangle*, *rickety-rackety*) or the left half (e.g., *chit-chat*, *mish-mash*). Additionally, in some reduplicatives, both parts can be meaningful units (e.g., *sing-song*), while in others, neither part is meaningful (e.g., *riff-raff*). M. Donka explains these positional variations by the prosodic well-formedness of the reduplicatives [5:133].

M. Donka identifies two main features that contribute to this prosodic well-formedness. The first is that the stressed syllables in both halves of the reduplicative should have identical vowel quantity. The second is that the consonants in both halves should differ as much as possible. For instance, the high front vowel [ɪ] is typically found in the left half, while the low back vowel [æ] appears in the right half. Based on recorded examples, the most common vowel change is from [ɪ] to [æ], followed by [ɪ] to [ɒ] [2:150]. Donka notes that the small group of reduplicatives with the [ɪ-æ] pattern appeared about a century before those with the [ɪ-ɒ] pattern [5:139]. Other vowel changes are also possible (e.g., *cherry-churry*, *feery-fary*, *gew-gaw*, *teeny-tiny*, *yolp-yalp*), but they are much less frequent.

Let's look at examples specific to each case:

1. The vowel [ɪ] in the left half of the reduplicative changes to [æ] in the right half. Examples: *bibble-babble* (meaningless chatter), *brittle-brattle* (hurrying), *chit-chat* (gossip, trivial conversation), *click-clack* (sound of a ticking clock), *crick-crack* (a sharp, cracking sound), *diddle-daddle* (violin music), *dilly-dally* (indecision), *dimber-damber* (leader of a group of thieves), *dingle-dangle* (swinging motion), *drizzle-drazzle* (sound of raindrops), *fiddle-faddle* (trivial matters, nonsense), *flim-flam* (nonsense, lies) *gibble-gabble* (meaningless conversation),

jim-jams (pajamas in nursery language), *knick-knack* (small ornamental objects), *mingle-mangle*, *mish-mash* (a mixture of various things) *pinkle-pankle* (sound of liquid in a glass container), *ricket-rackety* (unstable, shaky), *rickrack* (zigzagged decoration for clothes), *wigwag* (to move back and forth rhythmically), *wishy-washy* (weak, indecisive person).

2. The vowel [ɪ] in the left half of the reduplicative changes to [ʊ] in the right half. Examples: *bim-bom* (sound of a bell), *chip-chop* (sound of an axe), *clip-clop* (sound of horse hooves), *criss-cross* (crisscross pattern or movement), *ding-dong* (sound of a bell), *drip-drop* (sound of dripping water), *flip-flop* (sudden reversal), *hip-hop* (urban youth subculture and music style), *ping-pong* (table tennis), *wibble-wobble* (unstable, shaky).

In Uzbek, ablaut reduplicatives often involve the sound [a] in the first part changing to [u] in the second part. Examples include: *ayqash-uyqash* (mixed up), *qars-qurs* (cracking sound), *qalt-qult* (shaking), *yalt-yult* (shining).

Additionally, there are rare instances where [o] changes to [u] in Uzbek, such as *don-dun*, *shov-shuv* (noise).

In some instances, the reduplicative doesn't follow the [ɪ-æ] or [ɪ-ʊ] pattern, but rather involves different vowel changes. Examples: *Bubble Bobble* (a video game), *cherry-churry* (bird sounds), *teeny-tiny* (very small), *gew-gaw* (a flashy but cheap object).

There are also reduplicatives with a connecting vowel or syllable between the two elements. Examples: *bibity-bob* (movement of floating objects), *clickety-clack* (sound of metal hitting together), *flipperty-flopperty* (free, swinging movement).

In Uzbek, a similar pattern occurs, where [a] changes to [u] with a connective syllable, such as in *shaqara-shuq*, *tasira-tusir*.

In English, the first element of an ablaut reduplicative typically contains the high front vowel [ɪ], which changes to [æ] or [ʊ]. Other vowel changes are rare. In Uzbek, most examples involve the vowel [a] changing to [u]. In both languages, the vowels in the stressed syllables of the two elements differ significantly, and additional connecting syllables may occur between the elements.

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